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THE BALKANS IN THE NOVEL „THE BRIDGE ON THE DRINA“ IVO ANDRIĆ (TRAVNIK 1892 – BELGRADE 1975)

Andrić's literary work was dominated by narrative prose, but he was also interested in science, especially the ranges of history and culturology. Literary critics have many years ago noticed Andrić's tendency towards writing about historical topics. In his works, he is preoccupied with historical misfortune of „the borderline people“ from the East and the West. And Bosnia and Herzegovina, placed on the very border between Turkey and Europe, was the region in which one could get the best insight in the tragic collisions of different worlds and their cultures. His messages are connected to the tragic confrontations of different cultures on the Balkans, they never ceased to exist and they are today current.

Key words: Ivo Andrić, Bridge on the Drina, novels, Balkans, Bosnia, Višegrad, Serbian language.

I. ANDRIĆ'S LIFE AND WORKS- INSIGHT

Ivo Andrić was born in 1892 in Bosnia and Herzegovina (Travnik), which was then one of the Austro-Hungarian provinces. According to the data from the birth registry, Andrić's parents Antun and Katarina were Catholics (Поповић 1991: 10), but, on the other hand, there are information that his mother, Katarina Pejić, was a Serb from Travnik (Брајовић 2004: 40, 89).¹ Andrić graduated from The Great Grammar School in Sarajevo. He was the chairman of the Serbian-Croatian Youth Association, later known as Young Bosnia (Mlada Bosna) in the same town. Pan Slavic syllabus of this association was geared towards breaking the Austro-Hungarian country and uniting the South Slavs under the auspices of Serbia, which was a free country by then. Bosnia as a homeland (firstly ruled by the Turks for centuries, afterwards becoming Austro-Hungarian from the second half of the 19th century on), placed on the civilization border between the East and the West, found a permanent place in Andrić's literary and scientific works.

In 1912, Andrić entered The Faculty of Philosophy (The Royal University of Franja Josif) in Zagreb. He met many famous Croatian intellectuals, who will have great influence on Andrić's beginnings of literary, or more precisely, poetic works (Деретић 1983:

¹ In some documents of a later date (e.g. the correspondence of Ivo Vojnović from Dubrovnik, the reports of The Ministry of The Yugoslavian Kingdom), Andrić was represented as a Catholic Serb (according to Јовановић 1974: 83, Матуља 2000: 355), and in one of the documents, Andrić himself declared that (according to Брајовић 2004: 45). The population of Bosnia and Herzegovina was comprised of three basic religious communities – the Orthodox Christians (Serbs), the Catholic Christians (Croats and Serbs) and the Muslims (Serbs and Croats). The Austro-Hungarian census of the population of Bosnia and Herzegovina from 1985 gave the following results – 42.94% Orthodox, 34.99% Muslims and 21.31% Catholics (according to Стојановић 2008: 14-15).

559, Леовац 1993: 170). Andrić went to The University of Vienna for the second semester of his studies, where he attended the lectures of professor Milan Rešetar, who was a Serb from Dubrovnik by birth. Then, in 1914, he continued with his education in Krakow (Poland). After the assassination of the Austro-Hungarian crown prince Franz Ferdinand in Sarajevo (28th July 1914) by the revolutionary movement Young Bosnia, Andrić returned to Serbia. However, he was then arrested and he spent the whole First World War in Austro-Hungarian prisons (in Slovenia and Croatia), as well as in the house arrest in the village of Ovčarevo near Travnik. As soon as 1919, after the fall of the Austro-Hungarian country and the creation of the Yugoslav Kingdom, Andrić goes to the capital of Yugoslavia – Belgrade (Брајовић 2004: 69, 79).

In Belgrade he becomes a part of the diplomatic service of the new, Yugoslavian state. He will resume this position until the outset of the Second World War, at the same time committed to his literary works. What is specific about that period is that he „turned from jekavian to ekavian spelling and pronunciation“ (Деретић 1983: 560), as well as the influence of the famous Serbian novelists to his works. In 1926, Andrić was selected for a member of The Serbian Royal Academy. He spends the Second World War in Belgrade, where he dedicates himself to his literary work. Immediately after the Second World War was finished, in 1945, he publishes his novels: „The Bridge on the Drina“, „The Chronicle of Travnik“ and „The Young Lady“. The Literary Association of Yugoslavia presented him as the Serbian candidate for a Nobel Prize in 1958 (Брајовић 2004: 164–165).² In 1961, he received a Nobel Prize for his novel „The Bridge on the Drina“.

Andrić died in 1975 in Belgrade. He left his literary heritage to The Serbian Academy of Science and Art.

II. ANDRIĆ'S NOVEL „THE BRIDGE ON THE DRINA“ AND HISTORY

Andrić's literary work was dominated by narrative prose, but he was also interested in science, especially the ranges of history and culturology. In 1924, he defended his PhD dissertation „The development of spiritual life in Bosnia under the influence of Turkish reign“ in Graz (Austria). In his dissertation, he analyses the Turkish reign, which brought hard living conditions to the local population with its conservative law. Andrić provides an illustration, citing the Turkish „Book of law for subjects without rights“ (Kanun-iraja). It stands here that the Christians have no rights to build or repair their monasteries, they have to respect all Muslims, they are forbidden to carry any weapons or ride a saddled-up horse, they are forbidden to dress like Muslims do, they have to mourn and pray for the dead in silence, not disturbing the Muslims etc. (Андрић 1995: 35–36). Andrić draws special attention to a specific kind of tax – „danak u krvi“ („tribute in blood“, „tribute in male children“), which implied the Turks taking away the healthiest male children from the Christians to Turkey, for the needs of the Turkish imperial army (Андрић 1995:

²The Croatian candidate was Miroslav Krleža.

29–30). He described the period when Bosnia was under the Turks as „the five-century flood“, „the separation wall“, „the burden that oppresses all the way to the distant future“ and which „leads to the loss of customs and to the degradation in every sense“ (Андрић 1982: 109). In his dissertation, he also describes the backwardness which the Turkish reign brought to the Orthodox Serbs, Catholics and Hebrews in Bosnia, as well as the problems of one part of the population which had to accept Islam because of the social privileges (e.g. accepting foreign religion, unfamiliar language etc.). Those tones, which speak about the deep wounds European civilization suffered from after the Turkish conquest of Carigrad (Constantinople, presently Istanbul), will find their places in Andrić's literary topics.³ Literary critics have many years ago noticed Andrić's tendency towards writing about historical topics. In his works, he is preoccupied with historical misfortune of „the borderline people“ from the East and the West. And Bosnia and Herzegovina, placed on the very border between Turkey and Europe, was the region in which one could get the best insight in the tragic collisions of different worlds and their cultures.

In his Nobel Prize novel „The Bridge on the Drina“, first published as an edition of the Belgrade „Prosveta“ (1945), the author presented his literary and artistic vision of Bosnia in the centuries under the Turkish reign. The novel represents a unique four-century long chronicle of a bridge on the Drina, built under Turks, between Serbia and Bosnia, a bridge which exists to this day on the Drina, near the town of Višegrad. Andrić notes a wide range of events around the bridge during a long period from 1516, when the Turks started to build it to 1914, when it was damaged in the First World War. Andrić will write about small human lives and fates around the bridge during several centuries (children games, first loves, misfortunes and murders) and he will depict the political ideas of that time, concerning the bridge, which stretches between the East and the West, Turkey and Europe, Islam and Christianity. But, at the same time, that bridge will cause an unfortunate separation of the Serbian people, not only territorially – Serbia and Bosnia, but also in religion – the Orthodox Serbs and the Muslim Serbs. Actually, this results in the bridge being the main character in this novel by Andrić. The same folk myths and legends live around it; they go from one generation to another, but the Christians interpret it in one way, the Muslims in another. And while people around the bridge live and die, while the generations come and go, the bridge with 11 arches („luxurious structure of unique beauty“) lasts alongside myths, legends and the history of the people. In Serbian epic phraseology, the expression „the bridge on the Drina“, with an old Turkish word *čuprija* ('a bridge'), is used to denote something that lasts and never ceases to be. That is exactly where the author found his inspiration – presenting us with a chronicle of one bridge („powerful, beautiful and lasting above all changes“), but he manages to do it using many

³ In his dissertation, Andrić criticizes the European politics stance, especially Catholicism, towards the Balkans. Unlike his positive attitude about Bosnian (Franjian) Catholicism, he strongly disapproves of the Roman Catholicism. For example, he stresses that for one request from the Orthodox Bosnians (Serbs) for help against Islamisation, the Pope gave a condition that the population has to accept Catholicism, before it receives any kind of help (Брајовић 2004: 116). Even later, Andrić didn't change his attitude towards Vatican. In one letter from 1920, written to a female friend of his in Rome, he will call the Catholic capital – Rome – „the dark nest of the Pope“ (Брајовић 2004: 84).

different human fates, human sufferings, small hopes and aspirations of which only the bridge can be the witness.

This is how Andrić contrasted architectural beauty of the bridge (made from „regular and unmistakably cut stone“) with the savageness of the rough Bosnian region, tragic separation among people, among brothers. However, the writer used the same way to follow the inner lives of his heroes. He paid special attention to the deeply personal tragedies and spiritual breakdowns concerning the change of religion, especially when talking about historical personalities. The bridge is actually a work of a Serb who turned Turk, Mehmed-paša Sokolović. He is a historical figure, imperial vizier born in Bosnia and taken away to Turkey with other children in order to serve the Turkish Empire.

Objectivity and calmness in narration are the main characteristics of Andrić's expression, often followed by naturalistic descriptions. In the third chapter, for example, the Muslims punish and torture a Bosnian Serb Radisav to death, because he tried to prevent the Turkish construction of the bridge, not wanting his people to receive anything from the Turkish conqueror. The punishment was executed in a familiar, oriental way- impaling on a stake.

„...Without another word the peasant lay down as he had been ordered, face downward. The gypsies approached him and the first bound his hands behind his back; then they attached a cord to each of his legs, around the ankles. Then they pulled outwards and to the side, stretching his legs wide apart. Meanwhile Merđan placed the stake on two small wooden chocks so that it pointed between the peasant legs. Then he took from his belt a short broad knife, knelt beside the stretched-out man and leant over him to cut away the cloth of his trousers and to widen the opening through which the stake would enter his body. This most terrible part of the bloody task was, luckily, invisible to the onlookers. They could only see bound body shudder at the short and unexpected prick of the knife, than half rise as if it were going to stand up, only to fall back again at once, striking dully against the planks. As soon as he had finished, the gipsy leapt up, took the wooden mallet and with slow measured blows began to strike the lower blunt end of the stake. Between each two blows he would stop for a moment and look first at the body in which the stake was penetrating and than at the two gypsies, reminding them to pull slowly and evenly. The body of the peasant, spread eagled, writhed convulsively...“⁴

In this historical novel, some characters are represented as martyrs and saints. A scene in which a new conqueror, an Austrian commandant is met by the representatives of three religions (a priest, a Muslim priest and a rabbi) is a clear depiction of this. The Serbian priest Nikola has an almost mythological role, as well as the role of a patron. Following the same lead, we can see that Andrić has compassion for the century-long misfortune of the Serbian people. The author sees the tragic part of the Serbs which hopefully look across the Drina to Serbia in the Bosnian Serbs. For, there are their brothers who started a fight for the final liberation from the Turkish reign. Andrić knew that the writer is not always able to control his feelings. „By representing others, we reveal ourselves.“ – he will write in one of his essays.

⁴ Translation taken from Ivo Andrić's „The Bridge on the Drina“, first English edition in Yugoslavia in 2003 in hard cover. By Dereta Publishers, Belgrade, Yugoslavia, translation by Lovett F. Edwards.

III. ANDRIĆ'S LANGUAGE AND STYLE

Andrić's literary style contains elements of language archaism, which we can best see in his lexicon. It helps the writer create authentic literary as well as artistic pictures of that time. Alongside dialectic features, there are Turkish words in Andrić's language, which provide us with a true picture of that time, and which today represent an archaic lexical layer. In the first chapter of the novel only, we can, for example, find a few dozens of Turkish words like *akşam* ('the night'), *basamak* ('a footstep'), *derdef* ('an embroidery frame'), *kapija* ('a door, an entrance'), *kasaba* ('a small town'), *kaurin* ('a person who is not a Muslim'), *kuluk* ('unpaid forced labour'), *mahala* ('a part of a colony'), *nišan* ('headstone'), *simit* ('bread'), *turbe* ('arched tomb'), *ćeif* ('will'), *fildžan* ('a coffee container'), *hamal* ('carrier'), *čaršija* ('the city centre'), *džezva* ('a coffee cup'), *šargija* ('a kind of musical instrument'), *šehit* ('a Muslim who dies in glory for his religion, a martyr') etc. We can see that the predominant parts of speech are nouns, from all areas of human life, normally connected to urban civilization, Muslim social life and religion. As a good language expert, Andrić reveals those socio-linguistic components which followed the collision of the Serbian and the Turkish language. Therefore, he accepts the Turkish expression „čuprija“ for big and fascinating bridge built by Turks, whereas for one small bridge over the nearby river Rzav he says that it cannot be called „čuprija“, but simply – „most“ ('a bridge'), so, a Slavic word:

„Even though there is another river and another bridge, the words 'na cupriji' ('on the bridge') do not denote the bridge over Rzav, a simple wooden construction deprived of beauty, history, of any other purpose apart from serving the people and their cattle to cross, but exclusively and only the stony bridge on the Drina.“ (Андрић 1955: 7)

*

Ivo Andrić is the most prominent writer from the Balkans in the 20th century. The basic characteristics of his works are Bosnia as a homeland, Serbian literary tradition and Yugoslav political ideology of his generation (Деретић 1983: 559). His messages are connected to the tragic confrontations of different cultures on the Balkans, they never ceased to exist and they are today current. Even after Andrić's death, in the decades that followed, it was evident that the civilizational confrontations on the Balkans between the East and the West are still present. The war on the territory of the former Yugoslavia proved that statement. Some intellectuals and analysts are of the opinion that the West did not understand this Nobel Prize winner from the Balkans. For, if his works had been better understood, the world might have treated the problems on the Balkans in a different way.

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Ким Ђи-хјанг
Првослав Радић

БАЛКАН У РОМАНУ „НА ДРИНИ ЋУПРИЈА“
ИВО АНДРИЋ (ТРАВНИК 1892 – БЕОГРАД 1975)

Резиме

Иако се Андрићев рад превасходно одликовао књижевном делатношћу, и то прозном, аутор је читавог свог живота показивао интерес и за бављење историјском науком и културологијом. Књижевна критика је, отуда, одавно уочила ову Андрићеву склоност према књижевноисторијском темама, чиме је његово дело дубоко везано за традицију српске књижевности. У овим темама исказана је Андрићева преокупираност „народом са границе“, људима који живе између Истока и Запада, између две велике и по многочему супротстављене цивилизације. То је, уједно, и тема Андрићевог најпознатијег књижевног дела „На Дрини ћуприја“, које је посвећено трагичним сукобима различитих цивилизација на Балкану, тачније у Босни

и Херцеговини. И својим ликовима и језиком романа Андрић је помно пратио ову књижевно-тематску нит свог романа.

Догађаји последњих деценија на Балкану, као и рат који их је пратио, показали су, међутим, да овакве друштвене супротности нису напустиле Балкан. Но, они су показали и да српског нобеловца, Иву Андрића, свет, можда, ипак, није најбоље разумео.